

EUCloudEdgeIoT.eu

**Second updated
communication,
dissemination and
engagement plan**

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D5.3 – Second Updated Communications, Dissemination and Engagement Plan

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
CEI	Cloud-Edge-IoT
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
EC	European Commission
EUCloudEdgeIoT or EUCEI	Short Name to refer to The European Cloud, Edge and IoT Continuum, an inter-project umbrella initiative of which UNLOCK-CEI is a member and coordinator with the sister CSA Open Continuum
KER(s)	Key Exploitable Result(s)
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
SG	Stakeholder Group
TF	Task Force
VCAs	Value Chain Adopters
WP	Work Package

Abstract

This deliverable offers a comprehensive overview of communication and dissemination activities within the UNLOCK-CEI project, part of the European Cloud, Edge, and IoT Continuum initiative. It covers stakeholder analysis, campaign results, and impact assessment through qualitative and quantitative KPIs for the second reporting period, from M19 to the conclusion of the project in M30. The document also highlights horizontal activities like online presence, events, and community building. Valuable insights and lessons learned are summarised and left as legacy for future communication and dissemination endeavours advancing the Cloud-Edge-IoT domain.

Keywords

Cloud-Edge-IoT; Computing; Continuum; Communication; Dissemination; Engagement, Demand- Supply Dialogue

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Executive Summary

This deliverable provides a comprehensive overview of the communication and dissemination activities of the project UNLOCK-CEI and is the second and final update of the communication, dissemination and engagement plan outlined in D5.1, directly connected to its previous iteration D5.2 released at M18. The document covers indeed the main results and impacts stemming from the performed activities in the final 12 months of the project, from M19 (December 2023) onwards, within the framework of the European Cloud, Edge, and IoT Continuum umbrella initiative. The document outlines the purpose, structure, and linkages to other deliverables. It also details the main activities and the evolution of the assets, developed both by UNLOCK-CEI solely and as part of a joint effort within the Communications Task Force (TF) coordinating the activities of a multitude of projects in the computing continuum space.

With respect to its previous iteration D5.2, this report presents an updated results section. More precisely, the document is mostly focussed on the outcomes of various communication campaigns. It also highlights horizontal activities, covering the project's online presence, events, videos, news digest, materials, Zenodo community, and the community database.

Conversely, the stakeholder analysis, methodology, objectives, and KPIs sections largely remain the same as the previous deliverable. Therefore, it is worth mentioning that only the updates and changes are noted in this deliverable whereas action items that appear in D5.2 or D5.1 but are not mentioned in this succeeding deliverable remain unchanged from the original plan.

Key assets, such as the demand-side CEI radar and the CEI-LING tool, were further developed to offer enhanced functionalities and strategic insights.

The deliverable overall summarises efforts in aligning communication strategies with project-wide objectives, reinforcing UNLOCK-CEI's legacy as a cornerstone for future initiatives, including its successor, CEI-Sphere. The project's cumulative efforts over 30 months have successfully fostered knowledge exchange, engagement, and strategic planning, leaving a robust framework for the continued advancement of the Cloud-Edge-IoT continuum.

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1. Introduction

UNLOCK-CEI aims at unlocking the potential for accelerating the deployment of the Cloud-Edge-IoT (CEI) computing continuum. The project is specifically focused on the demand side drivers and challenges as well as the technology-driven innovations and business opportunities driving demand value chains. Effective communication, dissemination, and engagement play a key role in shaping the success of Coordination and Support Actions (CSAs) like UNLOCK-CEI.

In this second reporting period, we have continued implementing our strategy focussed on building a robust and collaborative CEI ecosystem via comprehensive communication efforts, targeted dissemination channels, and active engagement with a diverse audience. Our communication plan and the activities implemented so far follow the plan envisaged at the start of the project and ensure that UNLOCK-CEI leaves a lasting impact on the CEI landscape and to its recently funded follow-up action, CEI-Sphere. Such an impact is also maximised via the belonging of UNLOCK-CEI to the broader initiative, EUCloudEdgeIoT.

The "European Cloud, Edge and IoT Continuum" initiative, also known as "EUCloudEdgeIoT," or "EUCEI" is a collaborative effort aimed at advancing the development and deployment of Cloud, Edge, and IoT technologies in Europe. This initiative was setup in agreement with the EC and initially driven by the [two Coordination and Support Actions \(CSAs\), Open Continuum and UNLOCK-CEI](#) both consisting of a consortium of key partners from various sectors, including industry and research domains. These two CSAs have collaborated over the past two years to address both the supply and demand sides of the CEI continuum, ensuring a comprehensive approach to advancing CEI technologies and ecosystems in Europe. The overall initiative is supported by a wide range of [Research and Innovation Actions \(RIAs\)](#) focused on topics ranging the whole spectrum of the CEI computing continuum. To date, the whole initiative counts 56 projects that often interact and coordinate joint activities to maximise synergies and potential impact. With respect to the previous reporting period, the following projects, belonging to the cognitive computing continuum cluster have joined EUCEI:

- [INTEND](#) explores advanced AI to bring human-like intelligence to the computing continuum, enabling it to adapt, think, and communicate in a more human-centred way.
- [MYRTUS](#) enhances cyber-physical systems by integrating edge, fog, and cloud platforms through an AI-driven cognitive engine. It emphasises collaborative and decentralised orchestration, supported by interface contracts for functional and non-functional properties.
- [HYPER-AI](#) aims to develop mid-tier technologies and connectors that enable seamless integration across diverse computing environments. The project fosters adaptive hybrid ecosystems that leverage cognitive clouds and edge intelligence beyond current limitations.
- [EMPYREAN](#) creates collaborative collectives called "Associations," comprising IoT devices, edge resources, and federated cloud platforms. These Associations are designed to work dynamically and autonomously in a secure and trusted manner through a sophisticated coordination framework.
- [ENACT](#) develops advanced technologies to support a Cognitive Computing Continuum that can manage resources optimally across edge and cloud. This includes dynamic scaling, elasticity, and portability for hyper-distributed, data-intensive applications.

Overall, this new cluster, which started activities during 2024, focuses on advancing AI and computing infrastructure to create a seamless, intelligent continuum across cloud, edge, and IoT systems. By fostering human-like cognition, dynamic scaling, and secure coordination among devices, the cluster seeks to push the boundaries of current computing paradigms, enabling adaptive and decentralised processing across multiple layers.

1.1 Purpose of the document

The activities reported in this deliverable are based on the objectives, value propositions and methodology outlined in D5.1 “Communications, dissemination and engagement plan”, and focus on the second reporting period from M19 to M30 while D5.2 has covered the first 18 months of the timeline.

An overview of the main UNLOCK-CEI final results and insights can be also found in the 8 white papers, 11 success stories, 1 policy brief and various other deliverables published on the [project’s website](#) and [Zenodo channel](#).

1.2 Link to other deliverables

As WP5 Communication, Dissemination and Engagement has a horizontal role in the UNLOCK-CEI project in terms of communicating project objectives and disseminating results to target stakeholders, all deliverables are relevant to WP5 activities and represent the source of content for most of the website, social media and event-related activities. Out of all, however, the following deliverables are found to be most closely related to D5.3:

WP	Deliverable No.	Deliverable Name	Connection with this deliverable
1	D1.1 (M6), D1.2 (M12), D1.3 (M24)	Cloud-Edge-IoT Demand Landscape	D.1, D1.2 and D1.3 report on essential trends, definitions and market insights which are used as primary material to feed the communication content which is the backbone of the implementation of the communications plan updated in D5.2 and D5.3
5	D5.1 (M03), D5.3 (M30)	Updated Communications, dissemination and engagement plan (initial plan and second updated release)	D5.1 and D5.2 represent previous versions of D5.3
5	D5.4 (M12), D5.5 (M28)	Demand Side Radar	The Demand Side Radar is one of the main visualisation tools used to attract and engage with the project stakeholders as part of the dissemination and engagement activities
5	D5.6 (M18), D5.7 (M28)	User stories and policy briefs booklet	User stories and policy briefs are also key elements of the communication strategy to raise awareness and inspire stakeholders
5	D5.8 (M18), D5.9 (M30)	Sustainability Plan	D5.3 is connected to D5.9, released simultaneously, and its previous iteration D5.8, because the communication and engagement strategies implemented and presented in D5.3 are crucial for generating support for the exploitation of project assents and the sustainability initiatives and long-term objectives presented in D5.8 and D5.9.
6	D6.3 (M6), D6.4 (M30)	Data Management Plan	Collection and treatment of all data used to execute the activities here described were compliant what defined in the DMP

Table 1 - List of related deliverables

1.3 Structure of the document

D5.3 offers a comprehensive overview of UNLOCK-CEI's final activities towards the implementation of effective communication, dissemination, and engagement actions. The document is organised into the following sections:

- **Section 2 “Overview of main actions and assets”** updates readers regarding the European Cloud-Edge-IoT Continuum umbrella initiative and the key role played by the Communications Task Force (TF6). It offers updates regarding UNLOCK-CEI's communication assets, including its latest stakeholder engagement actions.
- **Section 3 “Communication, Dissemination, and Engagement Results and Impact”** delves into the tangible outcomes of UNLOCK-CEI's communication efforts. It discusses various campaigns undertaken by the project, such as the second round of the Value Chain Adopter (VCA) support and of EC Events, the continuation of the Industry Insights campaign and the final KER valorisation and impact campaign. Following a similar structure as to D5.2, the chapter also provides updates on horizontal activities, including the project's website, social media channels, events, videos, news digest, materials, and Zenodo community. Additionally, the chapter presents the final status of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) specifically connected to communication, dissemination and engagement, as well as their contribution to the project's overall KPIs.
- **Section 4 “IPR policy”** reminds the project's Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) policy in alignment with other related deliverables
- **Section 5 “Conclusions and Next steps”** summarises key messages of the deliverable and outlines the project's plan towards a successful handover of its results to follow-up initiatives.

2. Overview of main actions and assets

This chapter presents an update of the activities performed under the remit of EUCloudEdgeIoT (EUCEI) initiative, established since the beginning of the project, in continuation of what was started in the first reporting period, with a specific focus on the Communications Task Force (TF6). Subsequently, updates on the specific activities of UNLOCK-CEI will be provided.

2.1 Communications Task Force TF6

In continuity with the work presented in D5.2, EUCEI has continued to foster collaboration and alignment among diverse stakeholders via its [six task forces](#).

Among these, TF6, the Communications Task Force, has sustained its supportive role, with all activities progressing as usual across branding, community engagement, event coordination, and RIA activities' amplification:

Since Open Continuum concluded in August 2024, its role has transitioned to the Nexus Forum project since September 2024, ensuring continuity and integration with existing structures.

On the UNLOCK-CEI side, beyond the routine activities, its contribution to the TF6 was mostly focussed on supporting MetaOS event promotions (especially around their open calls) and contributing to two European Commission workshops in Brussels: the [MetaOS cluster review on 10 April 2024](#) and [the Swarms cluster review on 5 September 2024](#). These workshops benefited from the input of all the EUCEI Task Forces, reinforcing the collaborative framework within the CEI Ecosystem.

TF6's leadership team, co-led by Maria Giuffrida (Trust-IT, representing UNLOCK-CEI) and Catarina Pereira (Martel Innovate, representing Open Continuum until August 2024, now Amrita Prashad for Nexus Forum), continues to convene bi-weekly coordination meetings, supplemented by monthly TF-wide calls.

2.3. UNLOCK-CEI Communications and Engagement

In the latest 12 months of its initiative, UNLOCK-CEI has continued to contribute to communications and engagement TF6 overall activities via the effort of WP5, primarily focusing on demand-side actions, within

the larger TF6 context. According to our shared plan and strategy, the communication activities are conducted in a double fashion consisting of both dedicated “vertical campaigns” and continuous horizontal actions. This summary outlines the key areas of both types of activity, with subsequent chapters delving into more detailed analyses.

UNLOCK-CEI's efforts have been geared towards engaging and supporting end-users, stakeholders, and VCAs. This approach is evident in a set of targeted campaigns that have been organised and executed since M1. More precisely, in the reporting period object of this deliverable, UNLOCK-CEI concluded its **campaign #3, started earlier in 2023**, dedicated to support EC-led events and more precisely executing the Info Day for the promotion of five specific calls which was held on 4th December 2023.

It also continued the market-focused campaign “Industry Insights” (**campaign #4**) started in M12 (May 2023) and concluded in August 2024 with the last sectorial event. The campaign was conducted to highlight specific industry results, with dedicated brochures, spotlight use cases and a series of industry focused impact events.

It organised the second wave of the VCA support campaign (**campaign #2**) focussed on the consolidation and validation of strategies and practical applications with value chain adopters’ dedicated online events.

Finally, it conducted the last “KER valorisation and impact” campaign (**campaign #6**) during the last six months of the project, culminated with the organisation of an in-person final event.

Apart from the vertical campaigns, UNLOCK-CEI has been responsible for continuous “horizontal activities” that include the management of the website, social media channels, newsletter issues and community activities in cooperation with Open Continuum and NexusForum.

2.4. Communications, Dissemination and Engagement Assets

As a result of our communications, dissemination, and engagement activities, all main assets for the project have now been created and are detailed in the table below. In addition to previously established assets, we have also developed a [policy brief](#) with recommendations and the [CEI-LING tool](#) to further support strategic initiatives. These additions are better documented in the deliverables specifically dedicated to these, such as D5.7, D5.9 and D4.4.

Communications Asset	Description	Main Owner
Brand Identity and positioning	A cohesive set of branding guidelines and strategies that define and communicate the distinct identity of the EUCEI initiative. This includes logos, messaging, and overall aesthetic that aligns with the goals and values of the initiative. Already created in the previous reporting period, this asset is now consolidated and being referred to by new projects in the community, such as UNLOCK-CEI’s follow-up – CEI-Sphere, which contains a reference to EUCEI in its own logo and website	Joint Ownership UNLOCK-CEI and Open Continuum.
Website	The official online platform for the EUCEI initiative, serving as a central hub for information, updates, resources, and engagement with the broader community. It features project details, news, event listings, and resources. Recently, it has been expanded to include new project updates, event details, and additional resources, reflecting the initiative’s ongoing developments and growing community.	Joint Ownership UNLOCK-CEI and Open Continuum/NexusForum
Social media channels	Official social media accounts used for promoting the initiative, sharing news, engaging with stakeholders, and amplifying the reach of EUCEI activities. Over the last period, they have grown in reach and engagement, supporting regular project updates and highlighting new initiatives such as events and workshops. Platforms include Twitter, LinkedIn, and Youtube.	Joint Ownership UNLOCK-CEI and Open Continuum (until August 2024)

Community	A diverse network of stakeholders, including industry experts, researchers, and partners involved in the EUCEI initiative.	Ownership is mixed, with some contacts being joint (e.g., from joint events or TF6 activities) while others are project-specific. UNLOCK-CEI has specific contacts that are more focused on the industry side (see asset “contacts database”)
UNLOCK-CEI contacts database	Developed since the start of the project to house key stakeholder information, this database includes names, affiliations, contact details, expertise areas, and engagement history. Since its initial creation, it has expanded to include over 2000 community members as of November 2024, enhancing its utility for tracking engagement and tailoring communications and outreach activities.	UNLOCK-CEI
Demand-side CEI radar	A tool designed to visualise the main use cases within the CEI landscape, providing valuable insights for the initiative's main key sectors of manufacturing, energy, healthcare, agriculture, mobility and transportation. Presented in its demo version in the previous reporting period, the final outlook of this asset includes additional use cases and a better classification of their information, as well as additional filtering options	UNLOCK-CEI
CEI user stories and collection of spotlight use cases	A set of expanded industry-focused examples and case studies demonstrating the practical applications and impact of CEI technologies.	UNLOCK-CEI
CEI-LING Tool	A novelty of this reporting period, this tool is an interactive assessment designed to evaluate an organisation's readiness for adopting Cloud-Edge-IoT solutions. By addressing various strategic aspects—including organisational structure, technology, industry and market positioning, financial considerations, and risk and compliance factors—the tool provides insights to guide organisations in their CEI adoption journey. The assessment is structured as a short questionnaire and offers tailored recommendations based on the responses provided.	UNLOCK-CEI
Policy Brief and White Papers	A series of new white papers and a policy brief, offering strategic insights for future CEI initiatives was developed in this last part of the project. These documents provide insights and guidance for policymakers and stakeholders, drawing on recent project findings to inform and shape future developments in the CEI landscape.	UNLOCK-CEI

Table 2 - Summary of main communication, dissemination and engagement assets

2.5. Updated Stakeholder engagement actions

This section provides an updated view of the engagement actions introduced for the stakeholder groups initially identified as the main target audiences of the UNLOCK-CEI project in D5.2. The stakeholder groups themselves remain unchanged; however, this version of the table outlines the new engagement activities implemented to address their evolving needs.

SG	Challenges	Value	Engagement Actions
SG1 - Business Users	Lack of or incomplete knowledge about the benefits brought by the CEI paradigm shift, inability to engage with CEI providers individually in an effective way, gaps between individual and industry needs or struggles in sustaining the long investment cycles needed to adopt CEI-based solutions, poor strategic alignment between different company functions, skills gaps, inertia, risk aversion for critical infrastructure.	Better understanding of CEI potentialities in terms of concrete use cases and application areas, possibility for their needs and voices to be heard and transferred to providers, the understanding of industry-specific dynamics and market trends.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A market-focused section on the EUCEI website continues to communicate adoption barriers and opportunities. • Business users were engaged in a second wave of targeted value-chain adopter workshops in 2024 and through additional success stories showcasing successful CEI adoption. • Participation in new UNLOCK-CEI webinars and additional industry events expanded engagement. • White papers and policy brief were produced, helping translate individual cases into broader industry insights. • Final event highlighted sector-specific challenges and solutions. • CEI-LING tool enabled customised insights and assessments for business users' CEI adoption.
SG2 - Industrial and Technology Associations	Lack of offering of actual services and infrastructures, understanding of dynamics limited to the sector of reference	Better understanding of possible CEI -based solutions, service offerings, user and provider business models, learning from different industrial sectors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expanded engagement with associations like the European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud, and AIOTI through ongoing networking events. • Contributions from industry associations in workshops and success stories further strengthened cross-sector learning. • Involvement in the final event for knowledge exchange and collaborative
SG3 - Tech Providers and Tech Developers	Capability and scaling complexities, interoperability problems, logistics complexities, bandwidth bottlenecks and high costs, security threats, and data access control, inadequate knowledge about end-users' needs, struggle in positioning clearly in the new CEI supply chain.	Direct link with CEI business users and a better understanding of their needs, collaboration opportunities with research and industrial players, and a better understanding of their role and proposition in the CEI tech delivery supply chain.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Additional tech impact and vertical industry events provided new opportunities for knowledge sharing and preparation for future CEI infrastructure. • Continued insights from UNLOCK-CEI webinars on technological gaps and solutions relevant to tech providers. • Success stories and user cases highlighted in post-webinar reports and white papers provided real-world examples to inform future technology development. • CEI-LING tool enabled customised insights and assessments for tech providers' CEI adoption.
SG4 - Research and Innovation Organisations	Limited contact with the business community and market players, problems in understanding or testing the suitability and readiness of their research for the go-to-market, lack of specific skills or resources	Access to research insights based on CEI landscape radar, market data or projections, and test results via commercial feasibility assessment tool.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthened community of research projects through dedicated task forces • Participation in EUCEI webinars and industry events facilitated knowledge exchange on use cases and technological advances. • New success stories and user case reports disseminated research outcomes effectively to industry and policy makers. • CEI-LING tool offered insights into commercial viability, supporting research organisations in refining go-to-market strategies.

SG5 - Citizens and General Public	Low awareness about these technological trends and how a paradigm shift from cloud to edge to IoT affects their daily life	Understand the benefits and opportunities that can generate from the development of CEI demand.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Series of new social media videos and explainer materials provided easily digestible information on CEI benefits. • Final event and additional online content reached a broader public audience, improving general awareness of CEI impacts.
SG6 - Policy Makers and other facilitators	Understand investment priorities for the development of CEI, support the main actors of the CEI value chains, encourage CEI adoption, and reduce barriers to its development.	Landscape view of the technologies under development, their comparison and their market readiness also in terms of standardisation needs and maturity, insights for future funding programmes and the shaping of the next Large Scale Pilots	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CEI-related policies and initiatives were mapped on the EUCEI website in a dedicated and updated section. • 8 white papers and a policy brief were produced to summarise key findings, challenges, and strategic recommendations, offering valuable insights for future policy initiatives. • Enriched demand-side CEI radar tool provided more detailed data for policymakers on sector-specific use cases and needs.

Table 3- Summary of Updated Stakeholder Engagement Actions

3. Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Results and Impact

Following the structure of the previous deliverable D5.2, this chapter presents the results of UNLOCK-CEI’s Communication, Dissemination, and Engagement efforts. It is divided into two main sections. The first part details the four key communication campaigns performed in the last 12, three in continuation from the previous period and a new one. The second part focuses on the horizontal activities that support the initiative’s outreach, such as the website, social media presence, event coordination, and community management.

3.1. Campaigns

In order to better achieve its goals, WP5 has worked on the translation of the strategic plan detailed in D5.1 into a set of targeted communication and engagement campaigns. In the last 12 months of the project, four campaigns have been executed. They are described in the following sub-sections

3.1.1. Campaign 2 – Value Chain Adopter Support (Second round)

As part of the phase 2 “Engagement,” a support campaign to recruit Value Chain Adopters (VCAs) was initially launched during the first reporting period. In the subsequent “Validate” phase, a second round of the campaign was conducted. This round focused on promoting industry-specific events to encourage participants not only to engage with UNLOCK-CEI insights but also to validate these insights and contribute to discussions on future pathways for CEI technologies. The events, organised by the partner VDI and held on 29 February, 19, 26, and 29 April 2024, targeted the energy, agriculture, transportation, and manufacturing sectors. Each event included a presentation of UNLOCK-CEI’s findings on market dynamics and opportunities in the respective sector, followed by interactive discussions on market structures, scenarios, and future pathways for European technology providers.

Duration: M21 February 2024 – M23 April 2024.

Main Goals and Targets

- Foster active engagement with VCAs.
- Facilitate validation of UNLOCK-CEI insights by gathering feedback and perspectives from industry participants.

- Support discussions on future pathways within each sector, leveraging participant insights to inform strategic direction

Main Activities Performed

- Promoted VDI's sector-specific events in energy, agriculture, transportation, and manufacturing through targeted news articles, social media posts, and visual banners.
- Developed content that highlighted the events' role in validating insights and shaping discussions on future pathways, encouraging industry stakeholders to actively participate in these conversations.
- Engaged with industry audiences by sharing sector-focused updates that underscored the relevance of the discussions to the ongoing evolution of CEI technologies.

Main Results

This campaign successfully enhanced engagement with VCAs by focusing on validating UNLOCK-CEI's insights and fostering productive discussions around future pathways for CEI technologies. Promotional support amplified the reach and visibility of VDI-VDE's events, attracting participants who contributed valuable feedback and perspectives. This round of the campaign strengthened UNLOCK-CEI's connection with key industry players and provided valuable input for refining the project's strategic direction.

- Events supported: 4 sector-specific events (energy, agriculture, transportation, manufacturing) on 29 February, 19, 26, and 29 April 2024
- Social Media and News Outreach: Targeted posts and articles tailored to each sector, driving engagement and validating insights through participant feedback

Figure 1 - VCA round 2 promotional posts

3.1.2. Campaign 3 – Support to EC events: InfoDay 2024

This campaign was started in the first reporting period and concluded with the organisation of the InfoDay held in Brussels on 4th December 2023.

Duration: M17 October 2023 - M19 December 2023

Main goals and targets

The campaign entailed the following goals:

- Increase registrations and attendance for both onsite and remote audiences.

<https://www.eucloudedgeiot.eu>

[@EU_CloudEdgeIoT](https://twitter.com/EU_CloudEdgeIoT) | [in](https://www.linkedin.com/company/eucloudedgeiot) company/ eucloudedgeiot

- Facilitate meaningful interactions through pitches and booked meetings, maximising networking opportunities for participants.
- Support the European Commission's objectives for broader engagement and participation in Horizon Europe calls.

Main Activities Performed:

- Promotional Outreach: Utilised dedicated news, posts, and banners to generate interest and awareness, targeting potential attendees from relevant sectors.
- Hybrid event support and coordination with Open Continuum: Organised and supported hybrid settings to accommodate both onsite and remote participants, ensuring seamless experiences for all attendees. UNLOCK-CEI also synchronised with Open Continuum, which managed the B2match platform to facilitate remote networking and matchmaking.
- Facilitation of Networking: Enabled structured networking opportunities through a booking system and the B2match platform, allowing attendees to schedule meetings and engage in meaningful discussions.

Main Results:

The campaign, aligning with key EC events, has achieved significant milestones:

- Registrations: A total of 452 registrations, with 87 onsite and 365 remote participants, reflecting strong interest in both formats.
- Attendance: The event attracted 608 attendees, with 60 onsite, 172 engaging via B2match, and 376 views on YouTube, by non-registered attendants, highlighting the reach of the hybrid format.
- Pitches and Sessions: 37 pitches were presented across two parallel sessions, allowing participants to showcase project ideas and partnership opportunities.
- Networking and Matchmaking: 104 booked meetings were facilitated, supporting collaboration and partnership discussions.
- Marketplace Engagement: 85 marketplace opportunities were showcased, including 47 expertise offerings, 30 project cooperation opportunities, and 8 specific requests, demonstrating the variety of interests and needs within the community.
- Organisation Profiles: 112 organisations submitted profiles, broadening the network and fostering potential connections for future engagements.
- Poll Insights: During the event, live polls gathered insights on participant experience with EC funding, interest in specific Horizon Europe calls, and feedback on event priorities. The polls revealed high interest in particular funding opportunities and a strong desire for follow-up sessions, which will inform future event planning.
- Post-Event Activities: Event recordings were embedded on the event page to allow wider access to sessions, slides and the list of pitches were published, and outcomes were promoted via the News Digest. The B2match platform, managed by Open Continuum, was kept active until 23 March 2024 – the proposal deadline, allowing participants to continue networking and arranging meetings.

Figure 2 - Sample materials produced for the Info and Brokerage event in 2023 (campaign 3)

3.1.3. Campaign 4 – Industry Insights

The "Industry Insights" campaign, initiated in May 2023, is a market-oriented initiative designed to provide deep dives into various industrial sectors. It aligns closely with Task Force 5 "Markets and Sectors" and involves a series of sector-based industry impact events, complemented by the production of targeted brochures and digital content

Duration: M12 May 2023 – M27 August 2024

Main goals and target KPIs

The campaign entails the following:

- Host 5 industry-focused tech impact events to provide sector-specific insights.
- Host events to support the launch and dissemination of Open Calls of MetaOS projects among relevant SGs across various sectors
- Produce and disseminate sector-based brochures and digital content.
- Develop, launch and maintain the CEI demand-side radar and the CEI-LING tool.
- Engage industry stakeholders via events cross various sectors, enhancing awareness and collaboration.

Main Activities Performed

Part of the activities and goals of the campaign were achieved in the previous reporting period and reported in D5.2. In the latest 12 months of the project, the following additional activities were performed

- Continuation of a series of sector-based industry impact events (see more details in the section about events):
 - Agriculture online event on 20th February 2024
 - Transportation online event on 5th July 2024
 - Participation in the Medical Informatics Europe Conference between 28 and 29 August 2024, focussing on the health sector
- Delivered a set of workshops such as the *Pilot Factory* workshop (see D4.3 for more details) as part of the Alliance for Edge Computing and IoT Innovation (AIOTI) Days 2024 event in Brussels to showcase MetaOS results and discuss insights from the CEI-LING tool.

Main Results:

- Over the past 12 months, this campaign has effectively strengthened industry-specific engagements across key sectors, building a solid foundation for continued collaboration and influence within the Cloud-Edge-IoT (CEI) landscape.
- The combination of sector-based impact events and collaborative workshops has expanded the project's reach and visibility, allowing UNLOCK-CEI to deepen its connection with diverse industry stakeholders and position itself as a valuable resource for CEI insights.
- This phase of the campaign has contributed to the project's long-term engagement strategy, establishing valuable industry connections and gathering feedback that will shape future project

Figure 3 - Sample materials produced for campaign 4

3.1.4. Campaign 6 – KER Valorisation and Impact

This campaign was focused on showcasing the project's achievements and impacts and culminated with the project's final event

Duration: M25 July 2024 – M30 November 2024

Main goals and targets

The "KER Valorisation and Impact" campaign aimed to maximise the visibility and value of the project's Key Exploitable Results (KERs) by targeting relevant industry sectors, promoting UNLOCK-CEI's achievements, and positioning its outcomes for future adoption. Specific objectives included:

- Highlighting and disseminating project insights and results through success stories, white papers, and a policy brief.
- Strengthening UNLOCK-CEI's legacy and impact by engaging with complementary initiatives and industry players in edge computing, semiconductors, and cloud sectors.
- Organising impactful events to communicate UNLOCK-CEI's contributions and ensure the sustainability of its results beyond the project lifecycle.h.

Main Activities Performed

- Creation of knowledge assets: A set of 11 success stories was developed, detailing practical applications and case studies that demonstrate the impact of CEI technologies across different sectors. Eight white papers were produced, offering in-depth insights and guidance on critical topics within the CEI landscape. A policy brief was crafted to inform policymakers and industry stakeholders on strategic recommendations drawn from the project's findings and stakeholder consultations. All assets are documented in further detail in Deliverable D5.7.
- Positioning webinars

- Webinar with ALLpros.eu (September 2024): This webinar, held in synergy with the ALLpros.eu initiative, focused on edge computing requirements for the future chips and semiconductor industry. It provided a platform for discussing UNLOCK-CEI results related to CEI infrastructure and aligning these insights with semiconductor advancements
- Webinar with CISERO (November 2024): Organised in collaboration with CISERO, this webinar positioned UNLOCK-CEI results within the cloud sector, presenting the project's legacy in the context of ongoing cloud innovation and complementary initiatives.
- Organisation of the final event: the project's final event, held on 23 September 2024, served as a capstone to showcase UNLOCK-CEI's achievements, outcomes, and future pathways. It brought together stakeholders from various sectors, offering a comprehensive overview of the project's legacy and impact on the Cloud-Edge-IoT continuum

Main Results:

- Increased Visibility and Impact: Through 11 success stories, 8 white papers, and a policy brief, the campaign successfully communicated UNLOCK-CEI's achievements to a wide audience, solidifying its contributions and promoting the practical applications of CEI technologies.
- Strengthened Industry Engagement: The webinars with ALLpros.eu and CISERO effectively positioned UNLOCK-CEI's results within the semiconductor and cloud sectors, fostering discussions on CEI requirements and future advancements. These events helped connect UNLOCK-CEI with complementary initiatives, creating pathways for continued influence.
- Legacy and Sustainability: The final event on 23 September 2024 was instrumental in reinforcing the project's legacy, bringing together stakeholders to reflect on UNLOCK-CEI's impact and discuss the continuity of its results in the broader CEI ecosystem. The discussions and engagements during this event underscored the project's long-term relevance and positioned it for future opportunities. Moreover the following outcomes from the final event should be highlighted:
 - Diverse Participation: The event attracted 101 registrants from various sectors, including:
 - 40 representatives from universities and research & development institutions,
 - 14 participants from industry as business users,
 - 23 participants from the industry (providers, including consultancy),
 - 12 representatives from policy, government, and the public sector, and
 - 12 registrants who did not declare their affiliation.
 - Engagement and Attendance: Of the 101 registrants, 52 attended the event live, contributing to a dynamic in-person experience.
 - Key Sessions and Discussions: The event featured presentations, discussions, and panels that highlighted UNLOCK-CEI's key achievements and insights. These sessions allowed stakeholders to engage directly with project leaders, discuss sector-specific applications, and explore future directions for CEI technologies.
 - Post-Event Content: To extend the reach and impact of the event, a post-event video capturing key moments and insights was made available, ensuring that those who could not attend live could still grasp some ideas of the key messages stemming from the discussions.

Figure 4 - Sample materials produced for campaign 6

3.2. Horizontal Activities

In this section, we focus on the horizontal activities of UNLOCK-CEI, encompassing the continuous, overarching efforts that form the backbone of our communication strategy. These activities play a crucial role in sustaining the initiative's momentum, within the EUCEI wider efforts, expanding its reach, and nurturing an engaged and informed stakeholder community.

3.2.1. Website

As outlined in previous deliverables, in alignment with the agreement with Open Continuum and the European Commission, there is no dedicated website for UNLOCK-CEI. Instead, a joint EUCloudEdgeIoT (EUCEI) website was designed and developed to represent the collective activities undertaken by the supporting Coordination and Support Actions (CSAs)—UNLOCK-CEI, Open Continuum, and, more recently, NexusForum. This website progressively hosts information from all Research and Innovation projects involved in the CEI continuum, serving as a central communication and engagement channel for stakeholders. It provides comprehensive and essential information about the EUCEI initiative and its associated projects.

At the time of writing this deliverable, UNLOCK-CEI's successor project, CEI-Sphere, has officially kicked-off in October 2024. This fourth CSA is also represented on the EUCEI platform. In addition, CEI-Sphere will have a dedicated landing page to highlight the progress of its large-scale pilots, which are set to launch in January 2025.

3.2.1.1. Latest Website iterations

In line with the methodology outlined in D5.2, the website underwent a fourth and final iteration in the project's concluding year. This update included the integration of the demand-side CEI radar at the end of <https://www.eucloudedgeiot.eu>

2023 and the launch of the newly developed CEI-LING tool in the first half of 2024. The CEI-LING tool has been progressively enhanced with features such as the ability to save submitted answers, export raw data from the backend for submission analysis, and download a summary report from the front end, enabling users to retain the recommendations provided by the tool. Further details on the demand-side CEI radar and the CEI-LING tool are available in D5.5 and D4.4, respectively. To facilitate user access, a dedicated sub-menu item was added to the “Markets and Sectors” section on the home page, allowing direct navigation to both the demand-side CEI radar and the CEI-LING tool.

Figure 5 - demand-side CEI radar and CEI-LING tool implemented on the EUCEI website

Finally, in September 2024, a dedicated webpage was created to provide a centralised and accessible repository for all the main results of the UNLOCK-CEI project. This page offers direct links to key outputs and deliverables, enabling stakeholders to easily explore the project’s achievements and insights. Most of these results were presented at the UNLOCK-CEI final event, showcasing the project’s contributions and legacy within the Cloud-Edge-IoT continuum.

Figure 6 – Webpage with the project’s main final results

3.2.1.2. Website technical details

The website continues to be developed and maintained following SEO-driven principles, further enhanced by installing the Yoast SEO WordPress plugin. Comprehensive website analytics are gathered and presented on a customised dashboard, with monthly tracking conducted through Google Analytics to derive detailed statistics on website visitors and user behaviour. This proactive monitoring system allows tracking the project’s KPIs related to website performance, promptly identifying potential issues and implementing corrective actions. The Google Analytics profile was set up in the first month to collect datasets regarding visitors’ clicks on calls to action and conversions. Subsequently, a Looker Studio dashboard automatically retrieving information from Google Analytics was set up to easily monitor relevant website metrics and KPIs, as shown in the figure below, updated as of 12th November 2024. The graph below shows a website performance which remains positive and stable with respect to the results presented at the review in M18. We register a 61.4% engagement rate (still higher than the industry average of 50%), reflecting strong user interest and interaction. We have achieved 43,061 views and 18,928 sessions, averaging 4.2 sessions per user, indicating a consistent revisit rate. It is important to note that these metrics do not account for users who declined cookies, which may result in an underestimation of the actual number of visitors and sessions and could affect certain data insights.

Figure 7 - Looker Studio Website Analytics Dashboard

The website's hosting management, technical maintenance, and monitoring continue to be handled by the Trust-IT + COMMpla tech team, with administrative responsibilities shared between Trust-IT/COMMpla and Martel Innovate as established in the two-tier model outlined in previous deliverables. Hosting remains on Trust-IT's virtual servers in AWS, ensuring data residency within the EU, and automated monitoring via Uptime Robot is maintained.

3.2.2. Social Media Channels

To engage stakeholders, build its community, and gather input, UNLOCK-CEI has continued to leverage various social media platforms in coordination with Open Continuum, producing content tailored for each channel. The media teams of both CSAs implement a multi-stakeholder engagement plan, targeting primary stakeholders through social media coverage of internal and external events and reaching secondary stakeholders through ICT and business channels. This approach builds on existing networks and fosters interaction with the EUCEI community and related initiatives.

As of mid-November 2024, EUCEI social media presence includes active accounts on X, LinkedIn, and YouTube, with a combined community of 1,932 followers across these platforms—representing a growth rate of 64% from the previous year's collective figure of 1,180: Currently at 1,142 followers, LinkedIn remains highly engaged, attracting key community members, including CEI service providers. X has 687 followers, still improving, though recent policy changes on the platform have impacted engagement, leading to some decline in reach and impressions. The YouTube channel has 103 subscribers, serving as a platform for sharing event highlights, webinars, and project updates.

Overall, this combined growth reflects a more engaged community that supports UNLOCK-CEI's objectives for communication and dissemination. These platforms continue to provide valuable channels for reaching stakeholders, sharing insights, and promoting the project's outcomes.

The figure below shows some examples of more recent posts on our social media

Figure 8 - Sample social media posts

3.2.3. Events

During its last 12 months of activity, UNLOCK-CEI has organised directly a large number of events and taken part in third party events as well. These are tracked in a shared file with the whole consortium. The main events for the reporting period covered in this deliverable are described in the following paragraphs with a specific focus on those directly foreseen by UNLOCK-CEI Grant Agreement and the additional ones requested by the EC and organised within TF6. In addition to the events listed here, additional webinars and online workshops have been organised by TF4 and TF5 led by UNLOCK-CEI whose details are contained in the project technical report and other deliverables. The full list of events is also reported at the end of this chapter. For all the events, dedicated banners and digital promotion activities were produced as detailed in the “materials” section.

3.2.3.1. Strategic positioning webinars

UNLOCK-CEI has overall directly organised 2 main strategic positioning webinars to disseminate its final results with the main involvement of WP5 whose details are summarised below

#	Title	Date	Registrants	Live Attendants	Recording views
1	Semiconductors in the World of Cloud, Edge, and IoT	10 th September 2024	82	41	80
2	The future of Cloud and Edge technologies in the EU context: Market insights and sustainability roadmap	13 th November 2024	115	57	8

Table 4 - List of UNLOCK-CEI webinars in the period Dec 2023- Nov 2024

3.2.3.2. Tech Impact Vertical Events

UNLOCK-CEI has directly organised the remaining 3 tech impact vertical events on the agriculture, transportation (both online) and health industries (offline). These are additional but synergistic with the sector-based second wave of workshop waves organised by WP3.

#	Title	Date	Registrants	Live Attendants	Recording views
1	CEI Innovations in Agriculture and Crisis Management	20 th February 2024	149	83	82
2	Cloud-Edge-IoT innovations in Transportation: Market Insights and Use Cases	5 th July 2024	74	34	69
3	Market insights and health use cases booth [offline, hosted at MIE conference 2024]	28 th August 2024	N/A	Approx. 50	N/A

Table 5 - List of UNLOCK-CEI Tech Impact Vertical events in the last 12 months

3.2.3.3. EC Events

As detailed in the campaigns chapter, UNLOCK-CEI has been involved in the organisation of one EC event in this period. The event was hosted in Bruxelles on a full day on 4th December 2023. The event was also accessible online and streamed via the EUCEI website and youtube channel. The Horizon Europe Calls 2024 Information & Brokerage Session, part of the EU Cloud Edge IoT initiative was focused on topics like Smart IoT Platforms, Cloud-Edge-IoT Solutions, and Open Source for Cloud/Edge.

With 452 registrations, including 87 onsite and 365 remote participants, the event achieved a significant turnout, with a total attendance of 608 through onsite participation, remote networking via the B2match

platform, and livestream views on YouTube. UNLOCK-CEI and Open Continuum collaborated closely to manage the logistics of the hybrid format, with UNLOCK-CEI handling onsite aspects and Open Continuum facilitating the B2match platform, which supported 104 booked meetings. Additionally, the event featured 37 pitches across two sessions and showcased 85 marketplace opportunities, creating a dynamic space for stakeholders to explore project ideas, expertise, and collaboration requests.

Following the event, resources including recordings, pitch slides, and session summaries were made accessible [on the event page](#) and promoted via the News Digest. The B2match platform remains active until March 2024, allowing participants to continue networking. This campaign reinforced UNLOCK-CEI’s outreach capacity, strengthening stakeholder connections and setting a precedent for future Horizon Europe calls.

3.2.3.4. Final Event

The UNLOCK-CEI final event, held on 23 September 2024, provided a comprehensive platform for stakeholders from various sectors to engage with the project’s key results and legacy within the Cloud-Edge-IoT continuum. With 101 registrants representing academia, industry, policy, and the public sector, the event demonstrated the wide-reaching interest and relevance of UNLOCK-CEI’s contributions. Among these registrants, 52 attended the event in person, fostering a productive onsite atmosphere for discussions and knowledge exchange. The participant breakdown included 40 representatives from universities and R&D institutions, 14 from industry as business users, 23 from industry providers (including consultancies), 12 from policy and government, and 12 with unspecified affiliations. This diversity facilitated well-rounded discussions on sector-specific applications, the CEI-LING tool, and the insights from value chain adopter workshops. The sessions enabled attendees to reflect on project outcomes, address challenges, and consider future pathways for CEI technologies.

To extend access, a post-event video capturing key highlights was produced. This final event reinforced UNLOCK-CEI’s legacy and underscored the project’s lasting impact, positioning it for continued influence within the CEI ecosystem.

Figure 9 – Some pictures from the UNLOCK-CEI Final Event - September 2024

3.2.3.5. Overall view of events

UNLOCK-CEI has actively organised or participated in 23 additional events in the last year. These, adding to the 42 events, external meetings and sessions organised or attended in the first 18 months of the project leads to an overall count of 65 events that have helped the project enriching its own knowledge base and strengthening its position in the field. The table below provides a full overview of all the events the projects has been involved in, either as organiser or participant in the last 12-month reporting period.

#	Title	Date	Organiser	Location
1	Horizon Europe Calls 2024 Info & Brokerage Session	4 December 2023	UNLOCK-CEI (IDC and Trust-IT) and Open Continuum	Brussels
2	CEI innovations in Agriculture and Crisis Management	20 February 2024	UNLOCK-CEI (IDC and Trust-IT)	Online
3	Market Pathways for CEI in the Energy Sector	29 February 2024	UNLOCK-CEI (VDI)	Online
4	Meta OS Workshop: Ideas and Strategies for the Future of the Computing Continuum	10 April 2024	EC	Brussels
5	Workshop: Market Pathways for Cloud Edge IoT in the Agricultural Sector	19 April 2024	UNLOCK-CEI (VDI)	Online
6	Workshop: Market Pathways for Cloud Edge IoT in the Transportation Sector	26 April 2024	UNLOCK-CEI (VDI)	Online
7	Workshop: Market Pathways for Cloud Edge IoT in the Manufacturing Sector	29 April 2024	UNLOCK-CEI (VDI)	Online
8	20x30 Summit - Advanced Digital Skills	16 May 2024	LEADS	Madrid
9	Welcome to the EUCEI community event	23 May 2024	UNLOCK-CEI (BluSpecs and Trust-IT)	Online
10	Metaverse, XR and Data Spaces Compliance	12 June 2024	Privacy Symposium	Venice
11	Post Quantum Data Protection	12 June 2024	Privacy Symposium	Venice
12	Open Continuum Final Conference	18 June 2024	Open Continuum	Brussels
13	European Convergence Summit 2024	19 June 2024	ADRA-e	Online
14	Cloud-Edge-IoT innovations in Transportation: Market Insights and Use Cases	5 July 2024	UNLOCK-CEI (IDC and Trust-IT)	Online

15	Medical Informatics Europe Conference	28 August 2024	European Federation for Medical Informatics Association	Athens
	Swarms Project Cluster workshop	5 September 2024	EC	Brussels
16	Semiconductors in the world of Cloud, Edge and IoT	10 September 2024	UNLOCK-CEI & Allpros (Trust-IT and IDC)	Online
17	IoT Sparks	19 September 2024	IoT Sparks	Valencia
18	UNLOCK-CEI Final Event "Towards deployment of Cloud-Edge-IoT solutions across the computing continuum from market pathways to large scale pilots"	23 September 2024	UNLOCK-CEI (Trust-IT and ALL)	Brussels
19	Virtualisation (digital twinning) for electric vehicle (EV) batteries	24 September	R3-MYDAS	Brussels
20	Pilot Factory (AIOTI days)	25 September 2024	UNLOCK-CEI (Bluspecs)	Brussels
21	Cloud-Edge-IoT technologies at the service of European sustainable Manufacturing Industries (AIOTI days)	25 September 2024	UNLOCK-CEI (IDC, co-organiser)	Brussels
22	European Big Data Value Forum	2-4 October 2024	BDVA	Budapest
23	The future of Cloud and Edge technologies in the EU context: Market insights and sustainability roadmap	13 November 2024	UNLOCK-CEI & CISERO (Trust-IT and IDC)	Online

Table 6 - List of UNLOCK-CEI events in the last 12 months

3.2.4. Videos

As part of the project's communication and dissemination efforts, UNLOCK-CEI has produced two specific videos related to the final event, in this last reporting period. One video pill was used to promote registrations at the event and one longer video was produced to highlight the main outcomes from the project. Beyond these, full recordings of all the online events and meetings have been made available on the joint EUCEI Youtube channel. A complete overview of the 9 videos published by the UNLOCK-CEI project as a direct owner in the last 12 months can be found below. These, summed up to the other videos produced in the previous reporting period and the videos contributed by other projects to the channel bring the EUCEI Youtube to a total of 63 videos.

#	Type	Title	Publication Date	Views	UNLOCK-CEI role/contribution
1	YouTube Video	HE Infoday: Digital Platform for CEI Innovation through [physical event recording]	4 December 2023	156	Owner
2	YouTube Video	HE Infoday: Digital Platform for CEI Innovation through	4 December 2023	97	Owner

	[physical event recording]	Open Source and Software –Parallel session 2			
3	YouTube Video [webinar recording]	Webinar recording: CEI Innovations in Agriculture and Crisis Management	27 February 2024	84	Owner
4	YouTube Video [webinar recording]	Webinar recording: Market Pathways for Cloud Edge IoT in the Energy Sector	13 March 2024	491	Owner
5	YouTube Video [webinar recording]	Cloud-Edge-IoT innovations in Transportation: Market Insights and Use Cases	8 July 2024	71	Owner
6	YouTube Video Pill	Don't miss out on our final event in Brussels!	29 August 2024	89	Owner
7	YouTube Video [webinar recording]	Semiconductors in the world of Cloud, Edge and IoT (webinar recording)	13 September 2024	80	Owner
8	YouTube Video	Celebrating Unlock-CEI's achievements at the Final Event in Brussels	24 October 2024	68	Owner
9	YouTube Video [webinar recording]	The future of Cloud and Edge technologies in the EU context: Market insights and sustainability roadmap	18 November	XX	Owner

Table 7 - Complete list of videos from UNLOCK-CEI in the last 12 months

3.2.5. News Digest

The UNLOCK-CEI News Digest is a key communication channel of the EUCloudEdgeIoT initiative, collaboratively managed by UNLOCK-CEI, Open Continuum and NexusForum, with contributions from TF6 members. This digest disseminates the latest news and developments within the Cloud, Edge, and IoT continuum spectrum, encompassing various aspects such as events, news, open calls, and research papers. The News Digest offers a comprehensive overview of ongoing initiatives, providing insights into various themes like software engineering in the cloud-edge-IoT continuum, enabling technologies, market potentials, and future research directions. It is designed to keep the community informed and engaged with the latest trends and discussions in the field. In the last 12 months 9 additional issues have been released to the 850 subscribers, bringing the total to 19 Newsletter issues sent during the whole project duration. The whole set of releases is accessible on the EUCEI website [here](https://www.eucloudedgeiot.eu)

3.2.6. Materials

The communication and dissemination efforts of the UNLOCK-CEI initiative also include a set of materials designed to maximise impact and reach. This includes three distinct roll-up banners, one for general purposes, one specifically crafted for the upcoming InfoDay and a last one produced to clearly mark and identify the location of the final event venue in September 2024. To ensure consistency across various platforms, a series of templates, customized Zoom backgrounds, and social media banners were developed for each event. Post-event reports were produced for the online industry impact events and a dedicated flyer was produced for the participation in the Health-focussed conference in August 2024. Flyers summarising

the main project results were also distributed at the project final conference. Some examples of produced materials are provided in the image below.

Figure 10 - Sample communication materials produced

3.2.7. Zenodo Community

UNLOCK-CEI continues to co-manage and feed the EUCloudEdgeIoT.eu Zenodo Community with deliverables, key documents, presentations and communication materials. As of 15 November 2024, the community counts a total of 62 publications. Of these, 38 belong to the UNLOCK-CEI project, 4 to Open Continuum, 4 to both projects, 6 belong to UNLOCK-CEI and other projects, and 9 are submitted by other members of the EUCEI community. The full list of 19 materials published in the last reporting period and related statistics are available below

#	Publication name	Publication type	Publication Date	Owner	Views	Downloads
1	Distributed Machine Learning and Native AI Enablers for End-to-End Resources Management in 6G	Journal article	4 December 2023	ICOS & 6Green	23	9
2	Meta-OS Use Cases Overview	Other (Booklet)	15 December 2023	UNLOCK-CEI	359	265
3	EUCloudEdgeIoT at Enlit Europe: Innovating for a Sustainable Energy Future	Report	18 December 2023	UNLOCK-CEI	19	13
4	The research community booklet	Other (Booklet)	29 April 2024	UNLOCK-CEI & Open Continuum	1031	521
5	Empowering Smart Education: Cloud-	Other (Flyer)	31 May 2024	UNLOCK-CEI	133	51

	Edge-IoT solutions for Sustainable Energy Management					
6	Functional View of the Continuum Reference Architecture: Minimum set of expected functionalities	Report	14 June 2024	Open Continuum	177	158
7	Cloud-Edge-IoT Demand Landscape: CEI Gap Analysis and Opportunities	Project Deliverable	18 July 2024	UNLOCK-CEI	16	14
8	White Paper: Gap Analysis and Strategic Opportunities for the European Cloud-Edge-IoT Market	White Paper	23 August 2024	UNLOCK-CEI	55	47
9	Data-Driven Cognitive Production: Revolutionising Industry 4.0 with Modular Manufacturing Systems	Other (Flyer)	20 September 2024	UNLOCK-CEI & aerOS	18	12
10	Enhancing Power Grid Resilience and Scalability through FLUIDOS: Leveraging Edge-to-Cloud Orchestration for Real-Time	Other (Flyer)	20 September 2024	UNLOCK-CEI & FLUIDOS	24	14
11	Smart Energy Management with IoT and Edge Computing: Revolutionising Domestic Energy Use	Other (Flyer)	20 September 2024	UNLOCK-CEI & ICOS	19	13
12	Introduction of drones and implementation of Predictive Technology in windmill maintenance	Other (Flyer)	20 September 2024	UNLOCK-CEI & NebulOuS	19	11
13	Smart Media/City: Cloud-Edge-IoT	Other (Flyer)	20 September 2024	UNLOCK-CEI & NEMO	29	18

	solutions for modern-day Media.						
14	Optimising Energy Management with Predictive IoT Devices: Interoperable Solutions for Real-time Room Occupancy	Other (Flyer)	20 September 2024	UNLOCK-CEI & NEPHELE	32	28	
15	Market Pathways for Cloud Edge IoT in Mobility Sector	White Paper	20 September 2024	UNLOCK-CEI	77	70	
16	Market Pathways for Cloud Edge IoT in Agricultural Sector	White Paper	20 September 2024	UNLOCK-CEI	55	46	
17	Market Pathways for Cloud Edge IoT in Energy Sector	White Paper	20 September 2024	UNLOCK-CEI	96	76	
18	Market Pathways for Cloud Edge IoT in Manufacturing	White Paper	20 September 2024	UNLOCK-CEI	116	108	
19	Overcoming Barriers in the EU's Computing Continuum: Challenges and Future Directions	Policy Brief	31 October 2024	UNLOCK-CEI	31	29	

Table 8 - Zenodo publications in the last 12 months

3.3. KPIs measurement and contribution to project KPIs

In D5.1, WP5 had set up the following KPIs which were originally listed together with their due date and the plan towards that target over the phases of the project. The table was then reported in D5.2 with the status towards the achievement of such KPIs at M18. This third iteration of the table provides information on the final status of KPIs at M30. The data show a positive outlook with the vast majority of the KPIs well achieved or exceeded and only a few minor targets which were not fully met, with justifications included.

KPI	Target Deadlines	and Other supported/connected KPIs	Status at M18	Notes and deviations
Website visits	40,000 (M30)	All KPIs, as project dissemination effort	42,044* (exceeded) *This estimate is derived from the number of sessions reported by Google Analytics, adjusted to compensate for an average cookie rejection rate of 55%	

Twitter Followers and LinkedIn connections	1000+ (M30) 1000+ (M30)	LinkedIn Twitter	All KPIs, as community building effort	1145 followers on LinkedIn (exceeded) 696 followers on X (not achieved) 103 Youtube subscribers (additional)	The target of reaching 1,000 followers on X (formerly Twitter) was not achieved. This shortfall is attributed to the platform's declining relevance and engagement challenges following its rebranding to X, making it a more difficult channel to grow effectively. To address this, efforts were redirected to YouTube, which has emerged as a more impactful platform for our audience. As a result, we have surpassed 100 subscribers on YouTube—an impressive milestone, especially as it was not part of our initial targets.
People engaged via workshops	1000 participants overall (M30)		KPI 1.3 Identification of top 3 CEI use cases (WP1) KPI 2.1 Develop 25 service requirements (WP2) KPI 5.4 Multi-stakeholder community database (WP5)	xxx (achieved)	
Videos & Video pills	15 videos (M30)		KPI 5.2 visits to website and social media followers (WP5)	24 videos, including event recordings (exceeded)	
Video visualisations	1000+ visualisations (cumulative for all videos)		KPI 5.2 visits to website and social media followers (WP5)	xxx (exceeded)	
CEI user stories	10 (M30)		KPI 1.3 Identification of top 3 CEI use cases (WP1) KPI 3.1 Organize 5 value chain adopter groups (WP3)	11 completed (exceeded)	
CEI user stories visualisation	2000+ page views		KPI 5.2 visits to website and social media followers (WP5)	1162 (not achieved)	The target of achieving 2,000 views for success stories was not met. A key factor was that many of the success stories were produced and published towards the end of the project, leaving insufficient time

				for them to gain significant traction. In contrast, earlier-published stories received significantly more views—up to 10 times more—due to their longer exposure and the opportunity for repeated promotion. Additionally, our initial plan to boost visibility through pay-per-click campaigns could not be implemented, as the related budget was reallocated to support more events than originally planned, in alignment with requests of the EC.
Use case entries in the CEI radar	60 (M30)	KPI 1.3 Identification of top 3 CEI use cases (WP1)	70+ (exceeded)	
Participation at third party events	30 (M30)	KPI 5.4 Multi-stakeholder community database (WP5) KPI 1.3 Identification of top 3 CEI use cases (WP1)	30 (achieved)	
Policy briefs	4 (M30)	KPI 2.4 Identify 10 key actions, decisions or framework conditions for future market scenarios (WP2)	1 policy brief and 8 white papers published (exceeded)	Motivations for the adaptation of this KPI are provided in D5.7
Projects funded under HORIZON-CL4-2021-DATA-01-05, HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01-02, and HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01-03 participating at webinars	30 (M30).	KPI 4.3 20 supply side actors participating in cross-project CEI tech task force. (WP4) KPI 4.5 5 technical developer events by domain providing inputs for the feasibility (WP4)	50+ project participants joining our events also via the activities of the TFs (exceeded)	
Multi-stakeholder community database	2000+ (M30)	All KPIs, as community building effort	2000+ (achieved)	
Newsletters	10 (M30)	KPI 5.4 Multi-stakeholder community database (WP5)	19 (exceeded)	
Webinars	5 (M30)	KPI 5.4 Multi-stakeholder community database (WP5)	5 (achieved)	

		KPI 3.1 Organize 5 value chain adopter groups (WP3)		
Technology Impact Events	5 (M30)	KPI 5.4 Multi-stakeholder community database (WP5) KPI 3.1 Organize 5 value chain adopter groups (WP3)	5 (achieved)	
Online Forum Events	2 (M30)	KPI 5.4 Multi-stakeholder community database (WP5) KPI 1.3 Identification of top 3 CEI use cases (WP1)	2 (achieved)	

Table 9 - Status of Communication, Dissemination and Engagement KPIs at M30

4. IPR Policy

UNLOCK- CEI has produced over 120 different documents and materials, including presentations, videos, documentation, deliverables, reports and tools. The UNLOCK-CEI management of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) strongly favours wide dissemination, open access, and reuse (academic and commercial) of the project's results.

The project has applied an IPR policy that manages the IP generated within the project, and also includes reserving the rights generated by vesting ownership in the corporate project participants. The Consortium Agreement between the partners manages all IPR issues.

Whenever possible UNLOCK CEI adopts the following license for results:

Creative Commons attribution license CC BY 4.0 for documents, reports, presentations etc., unless otherwise agreed and for justified reasons. This allows sharing and adaptation of material as long as the work is appropriately attributed

All the material currently produced and suitable for public dissemination are being uploaded in the appropriate public official channels (i.e., website, YouTube and other social media channels) or repository (i.e., Zenodo).

Detailed Data Management activities are addressed in the D6.2 - Data Management Plan and its update D6.4 to which all activities conducted for Communication, Dissemination and Engagement purposes adhere for the whole duration of the project.

5. Conclusions

Over the past 30 months, the UNLOCK-CEI project has established a comprehensive framework for communication, dissemination, and engagement, contributing to meaningful advancements in the CEI domain. By fostering relationships with key stakeholders, including Value Chain Adopters, policymakers, researchers, and industry players, the project has built a diverse and active community. It has also developed sustainable tools and resources, such as the CEI demand-side radar and the CEI-LING tool, as well as policy briefs and white papers that provide valuable guidance for CEI adoption. Furthermore, the project has

facilitated collaboration across multiple European initiatives, ensuring alignment with Horizon Europe objectives and creating synergies for future developments.

As the project transitions to its successor initiative, CEI-Sphere, the focus will shift towards sustaining and amplifying the legacy of UNLOCK-CEI. The continuation of existing communication efforts, including leveraging the EUCEI website and social media channels, will ensure ongoing dissemination of insights and engagement with stakeholders. CEI-Sphere will expand the project's impact by supporting large-scale pilots, drawing on the lessons and resources developed through UNLOCK-CEI to address real-world challenges and foster innovation across sectors. The influence of the project's outputs, particularly its engagement campaigns and policy contributions, will continue to shape future frameworks and funding priorities for CEI technologies. Established relationships will also serve as a foundation for enhanced cooperation across sectors, driving further progress within the CEI landscape.